

HEMODYNAMIC STATUS IN PATIENTS WITH BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

O.O. Kenjaev

Central Asian Medical University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14940195>

Abstract. *Bronchial asthma (BA) is a chronic inflammatory disease of the airways that can lead to systemic vascular dysfunction and alterations in hemodynamics. This study examines the hemodynamic parameters in patients with bronchial asthma, focusing on changes in cardiac function, vascular resistance, and pulmonary circulation. The interplay between bronchial obstruction, hypoxia, and cardiovascular adaptations is analyzed to understand the impact of asthma on systemic and pulmonary hemodynamics. The findings highlight early cardiovascular assessment's significance in preventing complications such as pulmonary hypertension and right ventricular dysfunction in asthmatic patients. Identifying hemodynamic alterations in BA may contribute to improved clinical management and targeted therapeutic strategies.*

Keywords: *bronchial asthma, hemodynamics, pulmonary circulation, vascular resistance, cardiovascular dysfunction, pulmonary hypertension.*

Bronchial obstruction leads to alveolar hypoventilation, which in turn causes alveolar hypoxia. At the onset of bronchial asthma (BA), hypoxia is significant and occurs only during physical exertion and infection activation. At this stage, compensatory reactions such as pulmonary hypertension and increased myocardial function develop as indicators of tissue hypoxia and damage [8, 23]. In patients with chronic obstructive diseases, prolonged and pronounced hypoxia leads to the stabilization of pulmonary hypertension and the metabolic cause of myocardial dystrophy, which results in a shift of the energy balance toward the opposing side and a decrease in myocardial compensatory ability [20]. In the early stages of BA, myocardial hyperfunction, restructuring of blood circulation in a hyperkinetic type, increased arterial pressure, increased heart rate (HR), stroke volume (SV), and minute blood volume (MBV) are observed [22]. As pulmonary changes progress, initial kinetic and later hypokinetic disorders of central blood circulation develop. Some opinions suggest that hypokinetic-type blood circulation disorders can already be observed in the early stages of BA [20]. Eukinetic disorders are characterized by decreased SV, increased HR, and unchanged MBV. Pulmonary circulation studies reveal significant pulmonary hypertension associated with increased pulmonary vascular resistance and right ventricular overload. Pulmonary blood supply decreases [20]. In patients with BA, increased total peripheral resistance (TPR) and decreased SV are considered compensatory reactions to reduce stress on the left ventricular ejection fraction. Maintaining adequate blood supply is achieved by increasing HR, supporting MBV, and reflexively redistributing blood flow to organs [20]. Hypokinetic blood circulation disorders are characterized by decreased MBV, increased TPR, and reduced myocardial contractility. Such patients exhibit right ventricular overload, high vascular bed resistance to blood flow, pronounced pulmonary hypertension, and dystrophic changes in the myocardium [20]. One of the main mechanisms affecting cardiac output reduction is the increase in intrathoracic pressure due to prolonged exhalation and increased airflow resistance, which decreases venous return to the heart [20]. Observations by G.E. Gendlin

and co-authors indicate that in pronounced obstructive syndrome, a significant decrease in pulmonary blood flow is associated with increased vascular resistance, obliteration, and narrowing of the pulmonary vascular bed [20]. The effect of arterial hypoxemia in patients with BA impacts not only the systolic function of the right ventricle (RV) but also contributes to diastolic dysfunction, leading to impaired relaxation of cardiac muscles when PaO₂ falls below 50 mmHg [4, 10, 20]. Some authors believe that one of the earliest changes in BA is left ventricular diastolic dysfunction, with an increase in left atrial volume and impaired function [3, 28]. Right ventricular diastolic dysfunction develops later in moderate to severe BA cases [1, 3, 7]. K.A. Memetov and colleagues suggest that changes in blood circulation during an exacerbation of the disease are associated with functional myocardial changes. Increased MBV due to accelerated HR and SV and decreased pulmonary arterial and total peripheral resistance indicate good cardiac adaptive capacity. However, when SV is unchanged or reduced while HR accelerates, it suggests decreased myocardial strength and increased correct ventricular pressure, which indicates heart failure [20]. Thus, blood circulation changes in BA patients follow a staged progression. Increased cardiac function manifests as hyperkinetic circulation when TPR has sufficient compensatory capacity. Increased MBV enhances ventilation efficiency and oxygen consumption coefficient [10]. During BA exacerbation, SV and MBV decrease, which is linked to reduced myocardial contractility, pulmonary emphysema, increased intrathoracic pressure, and subsequent compression of significant vessels supplying the heart [20].

In the early stages of pulmonary hypertension, compensatory mechanisms maintain pressure increase due to enhanced cardiac output rather than increased pulmonary vascular resistance. However, as the disease progresses and anatomical changes in the lungs develop persistent pulmonary hypertension forms, reflecting the exhaustion of compensatory mechanisms in the pulmonary and cardiovascular systems [20]. Hypoxia is one of the primary causes of myocardial dystrophy and metabolic disturbances across vital systems [20]. Along with hypoxia, other mechanisms of cardiac damage in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) include impaired intracardiac and pulmonary circulation, infectious-toxic and immune-allergic influences, increased circulating blood volume and blood viscosity, vascular obliteration, disseminated intravascular coagulation, vascular fibrosis, and redistribution of blood volume between arterial and venous compartments [9, 24].

Conclusion: Thus, BA patients' intraventricular blood flow disorders correlate with the severity of the obstructive syndrome, with periodic changes in the pulmonary circulation and small circulatory system dynamics. Studying circulatory system disorders in BA may be necessary in disease management and treatment strategies. Bronchial asthma (BA) inflammation in lung tissues leads to metabolic dysfunction, which directly affects the state of microhemodynamics and induces significant changes in hematohistological metabolism.

A direct correlation has been identified between increased permeability of capillary-connective tissue structures and elevated concentrations of histamine and serotonin in the bloodstream of BA patients. These patients also exhibit disrupted metabolism of lipids, glucocorticoids (GCS), kinins, and prostaglandins, leading to impaired adaptation mechanisms in cells and tissues, altered permeability of small blood vessels, and the development of capillary-trophic pathologies. Morphologically, these changes manifest as perivascular edema, pinpoint hemorrhages and neurotrophic processes that damage perivascular connective tissue and pulmonary parenchymal cells.

REFERENCES

1. Eniseeva, E. S., et al. (2015). Hemodynamics and diastolic function of the right ventricle in patients with bronchial asthma. *Therapeutic Archive*, (8), 39-42.
2. Karoli, N. A. (2017). Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and cardiovascular pathology: Clinical-functional relationships and prognosis (Doctoral dissertation). Saratov.
3. Kozlova, L. T. (2011). Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and ischemic heart disease: Some aspects of functional diagnostics. *Pulmonology*, (2), 9-12.
4. Martynyuk, T. V., et al. (2017). Endothelial dysfunction in patients with pulmonary hypertension. *Cardiology*, (3), 25-29.
5. Nikitin, Yu. P., et al. (2012). Prognostic significance of QT and RR interval duration and variability. *Cardiology*, (2), 76-83.
6. Paleev, N. R., et al. (2019). Early diagnosis of ischemic heart disease in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Therapeutic Archive*, (9), 53-56.
7. Perley, V. E. (2018). Functioning of the right heart chambers and development of right ventricular failure in patients with chronic nonspecific lung diseases. *RMV*, (2), 9-13.
8. Sabadyshin, R. A., et al. (2013). Tissue oxygen diffusion in patients with chronic heart failure. *Cardiology*, 33(1), 58-60.
9. Sviridov, A. A., et al. (2020). Silent myocardial ischemia in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: Treatment options. *Russian Journal of Cardiology*, (1), 68-72.
10. Silverstov, V. P., et al. (2021). Chronic pulmonary heart disease: Mechanisms of formation and progression. *Therapeutic Archive*, (3), 103-105.
11. Simonenko, V. B., et al. (2021). Features of heart rhythm disorders and their treatment with diltiazem-retard in patients with bronchial asthma. *Clinical Medicine*, (3), 22-26.
12. Turaeva, N. O. (2021). Clinical, immunological, and biochemical features of bronchial asthma in children (PhD dissertation abstract). Samarkand.
13. Khayrullaeva, S. S. (2018). Clinical-pathogenetic characteristics of gastro-duodenal zone lesions in hormone-dependent bronchial asthma and methods of correction (PhD dissertation abstract). Tashkent.
14. Khankeldieva, H. K. (2019). Features of autonomic and thyroid status in children with bronchial asthma (PhD dissertation abstract). Tashkent.
15. Khodushina, I. N. (2020). Changes in hemodynamic parameters in patients with bronchial asthma. *Russian Medical and Biological Bulletin*, 1-6.
16. Kholiqova, N. A. (2023). Assessment of modern features of bronchial asthma exacerbation and optimization of rapid treatment-prevention (20-year monitoring results) (PhD dissertation abstract). Andijan.
17. Chernekhovskaya, N. E., et al. (2015). Systemic pathology in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. Moscow: Economics and Informatics.
18. Chicherina, E. N., et al. (2014). Myocardial ischemia and paroxysmal arrhythmias in different severity levels of bronchial asthma. *Clinical Medicine*, (11), 26-28.
19. Chicherina, E. N., et al. (2013). Cardiovascular system status in patients with different severity levels of bronchial asthma. *Problems of Tuberculosis and Lung Diseases*, (8), 25-28.

20. Shalashova, E. A. (2016). Diagnosis of early changes in the functional state of the cardiorespiratory system in patients with bronchial asthma (PhD dissertation abstract). Ulyanovsk.
21. Sharipova, N. S. (2018). Medical and social aspects of bronchial asthma prevalence and ways to improve them (Bukhara region case study) (PhD dissertation abstract). Tashkent.
22. Shkolnikova, M. A. (2021). Long QT interval syndrome. Moscow: Medpraktika.
23. Burdet, L., et al. (2017). Thermogenic effect of bronchodilators in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Thorax*, 52(2), 130-135.
24. Chazan, R. (2014). Salbutamol effects on left ventricular function and selected biochemical parameters in patients with bronchial asthma. *Polskie Archiwum Medycyny Wewnętrznej*, 92(4), 299-305.
25. Day, C. P., et al. (2010). QT dispersion: An indication of arrhythmia risk in patients with long QT intervals. *British Heart Journal*, 63, 342-344.
26. De Brayne, M., et al. (2019). Prolonged QT interval predicts cardiac and all-cause mortality in the elderly. *European Heart Journal*, 20, 278-284.
27. Dekker, J., et al. (2014). Association between QT interval and coronary heart disease in middle-aged and elderly men: The Zutphen study. *Circulation*, 90, 779-785.
28. Kohama, A., et al. (2010). Pathologic involvement of the left ventricle in chronic cor pulmonale. *Chest*, 98, 794-800.
29. Malik, M., et al. (2017). Mystery of QTc interval dispersion. *American Journal of Cardiology*, 79, 785-787.